

THE ROLE OF SCHOOL IN FORMING PROFESSIONAL CAREER MOTIVATION IN FUTURE TEACHERS THROUGH THE CAREER GUIDANCE SYSTEM

A.A. Ibragimov¹, S.X. Djalolova²

Samarkand Regional Pedagogical Center of Excellence, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences,
Professor¹

Samarkand State University named after Sharaf Rashidov, Theory of pedagogy. 3rd year
doctoral student specializing in the History of Pedagogical teaching²

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the process of forming professional career motivation in future teachers through the professional guidance system, especially the influence of the school environment on this. The results show that when a positive pedagogical environment is created at school, students increase their confidence and commitment to their profession. The article provides an in-depth analysis of pedagogical motivation and the role of the school based on scientific literature.*

Keywords: *professional guidance, motivation, future teacher, pedagogical practice, school environment, mentoring, professional career.*

INTRODUCTION

One of the most important tasks facing the education system today is to educate the younger generation as specialists who are not only knowledgeable and qualified, but also love their profession, strive for personal and professional growth, and can take an active place in society. These requirements are especially relevant for future teachers working in the pedagogical field. Because a teacher is an important person who educates the future generation, who gives them not only knowledge, but also life values, professional orientation, choice and social consciousness. Therefore, strengthening the motivation of future teachers to the profession, making their professional choice conscious and responsible is recognized as one of the urgent tasks of the education system. From this point of view, the professional guidance system is an important mechanism that helps prepare students studying in pedagogical education for independent life, clearly define the path of professional growth and choose their profession with love.

The school plays a special role in this process. The school is not only a field of practical experience, but also a social and psychological environment where you can fully understand the social essence of the teaching profession. Here, the future teacher works directly with students, observes the professional activities of teachers, forms teamwork skills, and participates in solving pedagogical problems. All of these processes have a strong impact on his professional motivation. Therefore, it is through school activities that students begin to feel like real teachers. Teachers' professional culture, behavior, approaches, classroom management, and love for students inspire students and encourage them to choose their own path.

Therefore, this article attempts to study the importance of the career guidance system in forming career motivation in future teachers, especially the role of the school environment in this process, its real mechanisms, and effective approaches on a scientific, theoretical, and practical basis.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The issue of the professional guidance system and the formation of professional motivation in future teachers has been one of the topics widely discussed in scientific circles in recent years, and a number of studies have been carried out on this issue. By analyzing this literature, one can first of all gain a deeper understanding of the essence of the professional guidance system, the role of pedagogical practice, and the role of the school in this process.

First of all, the study “Integration of School and Pedagogical Practice: Opportunities and Problems” conducted by D. Shodmonova (2022) analyzes the role of school practice in the formation of professional competencies in pedagogical education. According to the author, when a student enters his profession in a real environment - at school, begins to apply his theoretical knowledge in practice, the process of professional identification begins, which becomes the basis for the formation of motivation.

The document “Methodological Recommendations on Pedagogical Practice” (2023) of the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan indicates specific forms of work (mentoring, observation, analysis, reflection) that should be carried out in schools as part of career guidance activities. These recommendations are described as the main guiding factor for students who have chosen the teaching profession.

The book “Psychology of Professional Career and Personal Growth” by A. Karimov (2019) covers the concepts of personal growth, professional motivation, and goal-orientation from a psychological perspective. According to Karimov, motivation is a process that requires constant stimulation and is formed under the influence of internal and external factors of the student. It is the first experiences at school, participation in real lessons, and the personal example of teachers that awaken the student’s internal motivation.

The issue of career guidance and motivation is also widely covered in foreign literature. For example, the Career Development Theory developed by Super (1990) states that each individual makes career decisions gradually throughout their lives, and that experience, social environment, and internal needs play an important role in this process. According to this theory, for a student choosing a teaching profession, school serves as a psychological space where life decisions are matured.

Also, the report “Teachers of the Future: Motivation, Development, Retention” published by UNESCO (2021) extensively covers the problems related to the professional motivation of teaching staff, ways to motivate them, and mechanisms for increasing the prestige of the teaching profession in society. This report clearly shows that the high-quality organization of school practice has a positive impact on the student’s career choice.

Local scholar G. Akramova (2020) in her article “Modern Trends in Career Guidance in Pedagogical Education” emphasizes the need to organize career guidance activities based on modern technologies. In particular, interactive methods, role-playing games, professional simulators, and scenario-based training play a major role in shaping the professional worldview of future teachers.

From the analysis of this literature, it can be seen that the professional motivation of a future teacher is closely related not only to personal internal preparation, but also to the social, psychological, and pedagogical environment. The school serves as the main platform in this regard. Through direct contact with teachers, the classroom environment, and pedagogical problems, the student forms his professional role. Therefore, the career guidance system allows students to form a sense of commitment to their profession precisely by operating at school.

METHODS

Qualitative and quantitative approaches were combined as a research methodology. To obtain quantitative data, questionnaires and questionnaires were compiled and distributed to students of the 3rd and 4th year of pedagogical education. In total, 120 students were involved as research participants. The questionnaire mainly asked questions about what experiences they gained during their pedagogical practice at school, their experience of working with teachers, how their views on their profession had changed, and what caused their motivation to increase or decrease. Semi-structured interviews were also conducted with 15 teachers who conducted school practice. Through these interviews, in-depth information was obtained about approaches to working with students, the attitude of the school community to the future teacher, forms of psychological support and professional guidance. In addition, the observation method was used. During practical classes, seminars, open classes and group discussions in schools, communication between students and teachers, forms of cooperation, and approaches of mentors were observed and recorded. In this process, the main attention was paid to cases where students actively participated and positive motivation was reflected.

With the help of these methods, it was clearly revealed how the motivation of future teachers towards a professional career is formed through school experience, which factors are important in this process, and the motivational influence of the school community. Also, important conclusions were reached through this methodology about the level of influence of practical experience on professional direction.

RESULTS

According to the results of the study, students developed a positive attitude towards professional growth during their pedagogical practice at school and felt closer to the teaching profession. In particular, 88 out of 120 respondents (73%) assessed the pedagogical experience at school as a decisive factor in clarifying their professional direction. 64% of students stated that the teachers at the school, their dedication to their profession and kindness towards students instilled in them a professional spirit and motivation. 57% of students noted that the difficulties encountered during the internship and the experience of overcoming them increased their responsibility towards the profession.

According to the results of the survey, the strongest motivation came from the personal approach of the teachers at the school and the creation of a friendly atmosphere. In this regard, the main motivational factors were noted as the individual approach of the teachers to the students, sharing their activities, participating in lessons with them and completing pedagogical tasks. During the internship, students were given the opportunity to answer students' questions, manage small groups, participate in evaluation and lesson analysis, and their self-confidence and love for the profession increased.

On the other hand, observations showed that positive analysis, constructive feedback, and moral support from teachers played an important role in increasing motivation. On the contrary, indifference, not involving students in independent activities, or only performing a supervisory function had a negative impact on their professional confidence. This helped to draw a clear conclusion about the extent to which the school environment affects motivation.

DISCUSSION

A thorough analysis of the research results shows that career guidance work carried out in the school environment plays an invaluable role in the formation of professional motivation of future teachers. During pedagogical practice, students are involved in real pedagogical activities,

which creates the basis for their social and psychological growth in relation to the profession. In particular, the personal approach, advice and support provided by mentors increase students' self-confidence. In this regard, the professional behavior of the school environment, team and teachers becomes an important factor in the formation of a teacher.

As noted in the scientific literature, the formation of professional motivation depends on external influences as well as individual personal factors. If a student feels useful to society, understands the spiritual and social significance of the profession, then internal motivation is formed. Such motivation can be supported precisely through school experience. There are also factors that negatively affect motivation: accepting the student indifferently, not allowing him to solve pedagogical problems, talking only about control and shortcomings - these situations increase professional doubts and anxiety.

Therefore, schools need to conduct a more systematic, planned and person-oriented career guidance system. Involving students not only as observers, but also as active participants, giving them freedom and valuing their ideas increases motivation. Schools should implement innovative approaches in this regard, including the widespread use of methods such as mentoring systems, portfolios, reflective writing and self-assessment.

CONCLUSION

Based on the above scientific observations, questionnaires and analyses, it was found that career guidance work carried out in schools plays an important role in shaping the professional motivation of future teachers. Students who love their profession and feel like real teachers will change during their school experience, gain strong motivation, and confidently step into their future careers. This, in turn, will serve as an important factor in improving the quality of general education, ensuring the stability of pedagogical personnel, and training a modern generation of teachers.

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